

Internet Banking and Bank Stability: Assessing the Effects on Liquidity and Asset Quality in Nigerian Commercial Banks

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Abstract

This study investigated how internet banking correlates with bank stability, with particular emphasis on liquidity and asset quality, using evidence from Nigerian commercial banks. The analysis draws on panel data from the published accounts of eight internationally licensed banks over the period 2015 to 2022. Employing an *ex-post facto* research design, both descriptive and inferential statistical techniques were utilized to examine the hypothesized relationships. Findings indicate that internet banking exerts a statistically significant positive effect on bank liquidity, suggesting that digital banking channels may enhance short-term funding flexibility and operational efficiency. Notwithstanding, internet banking could not exert significant influence on asset quality, indicating that credit risk exposures remain largely unaffected by the expansion of digital banking services. Furthermore, liquidity did not significantly moderate the relationship between internet banking and asset quality. These results suggest a level of institutional resilience and adherence to global credit risk management practices, despite the growing digitization of banking operations. The study recommends amongst others that commercial banks maintain strict compliance with credit management guidelines to safeguard asset quality in the face of expanding internet banking services.

Keywords: Authorization license; bank stability, banking operations; credit risk, digital banking.

JEL Classification: G21, G32, O33.

1. Introduction

The banking sector occupies a central position in the economic development and transformation agenda of modern economies. As noted by Sanusi (2013), banks serve as critical intermediaries in mobilizing and allocating financial resources, thereby advancing the financial capabilities of national economies. In recent decades, the sector has undergone profound transformation driven by rapid technological advancements; most notably, the emergence and diffusion of internet banking which has become a key component of digital banking that has reshaped banking operations globally (Khanchel, 2019; Ezie, Ghose & Maji, 2022; Musa & Joshua, 2023).

The accelerated adoption of digital technologies has prompted commercial banks worldwide to increasingly integrate internet banking platforms into their service delivery processes. This shift enables banks to improve operational efficiency, broaden financial inclusion, and enhance customer experience in an intensely competitive and evolving marketplace (Sardana & Singhania, 2018; Oyedokun, Orenuga, & Adeolu-Akande, 2021; Mbagwu & Obonofiemro, 2023). However, the growing reliance on internet-based banking channels introduces new dynamics that may have far-reaching implications for banks' liquidity positions and, by extension, their asset quality. As Jeroh (2019) observes, the

technological shift inherent in internet banking may influence the liquidity profiles of commercial banks, thereby shaping their ability to maintain sound financial health.

Liquidity remains a cornerstone of financial stability, and its management becomes even more critical in digitalized banking environments. Internet banking platforms facilitate real-time transfers, swift withdrawals, and rapid account settlements, all of which may alter customer transaction behaviour and, consequently, the liquidity conditions of commercial banks. In the Nigerian context where payment digitization is expanding rapidly, understanding how internet banking affects liquidity dynamics is therefore of significant policy and managerial relevance.

Beyond liquidity considerations, the implications of internet banking for asset quality warrant careful scrutiny. Digital banking ecosystems expose financial institutions to novel risks, including cyber threats, fraud, and operational vulnerabilities, with potential repercussions for loan performance and overall balance sheet health. Identifying how such risks manifest and the extent to which they influence the asset quality of Nigerian commercial banks is essential for sustaining robust risk management frameworks in the digital era.

Against this backdrop, the nexus between internet banking, liquidity dynamics, and asset quality presents an important yet underexplored area of inquiry, particularly within the Nigerian banking sector. This study seeks to deepen the understanding of how the adoption of internet banking shapes liquidity and asset quality outcomes in Nigerian commercial banks. The insights generated will be valuable for policymakers, regulators, and industry practitioners in designing strategies that promote the resilience and sustainability of the banking sector amid rapid digital transformation.

1.1 Statement of the Problem

Nigeria, a major player in the African financial system, has witnessed significant growth in the adoption of internet banking services in recent years. The convenience, speed, and accessibility offered by digital platforms have attracted a rapidly expanding customer base, fundamentally altering banks' interaction channels and operational processes. As financial institutions navigate this digital transition, the implications for key banking indicators, particularly liquidity and asset quality, have become subjects of increasing scholarly and regulatory concern (Jeroh, 2019; Ibekwe, 2021). Understanding how these dimensions intersect is vital for ensuring a stable, innovative, and well-regulated financial sector.

Globally, digital technologies have ushered in a new era of banking practices, and Nigeria is no exception (Osiolo & Sije, 2023). The widespread adoption of internet banking has provided customers with unprecedented access to financial services, including credit facilities and a range of transactional products. While these platforms may enhance bank revenues through increased transaction volumes and interest earnings, the ease of access to credit and rapid transaction capabilities may exert pressure on

banks' asset quality. Poor credit assessment, fraud risks, and operational lapses associated with digital channels could potentially weaken loan performance and impair asset quality.

This study focuses specifically on Nigerian commercial banks with international authorization licenses, which are at the forefront of digital banking innovation. Despite their advanced technological infrastructure, there remains limited empirical evidence on how internet banking adoption affects their liquidity and asset quality. This knowledge gap is particularly concerning given that these banks play an outsized role in shaping financial stability and influencing market confidence. Analyzing the interplay among internet banking, liquidity, and asset quality thus provides critical insight into how digital transformation is reshaping risk profiles and stability considerations within the Nigerian banking landscape.

The central problem addressed in this study is therefore the need to understand how the integration of internet banking services influences the liquidity positions and asset quality of Nigerian commercial banks. As the financial sector embraces digitalization, the potential opportunities and risks associated with this shift must be rigorously examined to inform effective regulation and strategic decision-making. The findings of this study will offer valuable guidance to bank managers and regulators such as the Central Bank of Nigeria among others, on designing policies that safeguard financial stability while fostering innovation.

Accordingly, this study tests the following hypotheses:

- H₀₁:** Internet banking has no significant relationship with the asset quality of commercial banks in Nigeria.
- H₀₂:** Internet banking does not significantly influence the liquidity of commercial banks in Nigeria.
- H₀₃:** Liquidity does not significantly moderate the relationship between internet banking and the asset quality of commercial banks in Nigeria.

2.0 Conceptual and Literature Review

Internet banking has expanded rapidly since the late 1990s, evolving from early electronic banking tools, like personal computers and automated teller machines (ATMs) into sophisticated web-based platforms used by millions worldwide (OECD, 2001). The shift from dial-up PC access to seamless interaction via internet-enabled devices, including smartphones and tablets, has enabled customers to execute a broad range of financial transactions remotely.

Internet banking is commonly defined as the digital provision of account access, financial management, and intermediation services through web browsers or mobile applications (Kaleem et al., 2019; Amaduche, Babatunde & Adediji, 2020; Oyedokun, & Oyetunji, 2022). Its development has positioned

it as a core component of modern banking, allowing customers to manage their finances independent of physical branches.

Convenience remains one of its most notable advantages. Internet banking enables users to monitor balances, transfer funds, pay bills, and apply for credit at any time and from any location with internet connectivity (Gallardo, 2013; Oyedokun, G.E, & Osho, 2023). These capabilities enhance banking accessibility, streamline payment processes, and improve financial oversight (Haque, Rahman & Kamal, 2019; Singh & Arora, 2017). Users can also access transaction histories, generate digital statements, and automate recurring payments, contributing to greater efficiency in personal financial management.

Research further suggests that internet banking supports improved financial literacy, as real-time account information and integrated online tools help customers make more informed financial decisions and better understand available financial products (Broek, 2016).

Overall, the evolution of internet banking reflects its growing significance in enhancing customer autonomy, operational efficiency, and financial decision-making within contemporary banking systems.

2.3 Concept of Liquidity

Bank liquidity refers to a bank's capacity to meet its short-term financial obligations as they fall due, using cash or assets that can be readily converted into cash. Adequate liquidity is fundamental to the smooth functioning of banking institutions, as it underpins depositor confidence, supports day-to-day operations, and serves as a critical safeguard against financial distress.

The growing integration of internet banking into traditional banking systems has renewed concerns regarding its implications for liquidity management. As digital platforms enable faster withdrawals, real-time transfers, and increased transaction volumes, banks may experience heightened liquidity pressures, making effective liquidity oversight essential for maintaining resilience. Regulators and stakeholders therefore view liquidity as a key indicator of stability in a rapidly digitalizing financial environment.

Empirical evidence on the relationship between internet banking and bank liquidity remains mixed (Rauf, Qiang & Sajid, 2014; Yasin, 2018). These inconclusive findings underscore the need for further investigation, particularly within emerging economies experiencing rapid digital adoption. Understanding how internet banking interacts with liquidity dynamics is thus crucial for assessing the overall stability of the banking sector in the digital age and forms a central focus of the present study.

2.4 Theoretical Framework

2.4.1 Diffusion Innovation Theory (DIT)

The Diffusion of Innovation Theory by Rogers (2003) offers a useful lens for understanding how internet banking is adopted by both customers and financial institutions. The theory explains the spread of new technologies through five stages – knowledge, persuasion, decision, implementation, and confirmation. Each of these stages contribute to shaping the likelihood and intensity of the adoption of a given technology. In the context of internet banking, customers first become aware of the service, evaluate its usefulness, decide to adopt it, integrate it into routine transactions, and subsequently assess its value.

Adoption is influenced by perceived usefulness, ease of use, compatibility with existing practices, and social influence (Davis, 1989; Rogers, 2003). For banks, organizational capabilities, regulatory conditions, competitive pressures, and customer demand also play critical roles in determining the extent and speed of adoption (Magableh, Khasawneh & Smedley, 2018).

The diffusion of internet banking has been linked to improvements in operational efficiency, customer satisfaction, service reach, and financial performance, as well as shifts in key risk indicators such as liquidity and asset quality (Jayawardhena & Foley, 2009; Riquelme & Rios, 2010).

Thus, DIT provides a relevant theoretical foundation for examining how the adoption of internet banking influences liquidity and asset quality in commercial banks.

2.5 Empirical Review

A substantial body of empirical literature has examined internet banking, liquidity, and asset quality across various jurisdictions. Alhassan, Brobbey and Asamoah (2013) analyzed data from 25 Ghanaian banks (2005–2010) using Random Effects and AR(1) models, and found that increases in non-performing loans (NPLs) significantly deteriorate asset quality and exert persistent effects on lending behaviour. Their findings underscore the long-term implications of asset quality shocks on bank operations.

Meihami, Varmaghani and Meihami (2013) used survey data from 42 bank employees in Iran to assess how electronic banking influences profitability. Using ANOVA, t-tests, and regression techniques, they reported that ATMs exerted the strongest positive effect on profitability. While informative for understanding electronic banking generally, their findings do not address liquidity or asset quality implications, particularly within the Nigerian context.

Adewoye (2013), using primary data from 140 bank employees in Lagos, found that mobile banking enhances service delivery by reducing transaction costs and improving convenience. However, the

study did not examine how digital service channels influence liquidity positions or asset quality indicators.

Similarly, Alagh and Emeka (2014) evaluated the concept of cashless banking which was proxied by ATM, POS, and web-based transactions and determined its effect on return on equity (ROE) in Nigeria using OLS regression. The study reported that web-based transactions exhibited a negative relationship with ROE, while ATM and POS transactions showed positive effects. Although the study highlights profitability consequences of digital channels, it did not explore their effects on liquidity or asset quality.

Yasin (2018) investigated online banking and performance among Ethiopian commercial banks using panel data (2010–2016). Employing random effects regression, the study documented a positive but statistically insignificant relationship between internet banking, liquidity, and overall performance. This suggests the need for further empirical scrutiny, particularly in environments with higher digital adoption rates.

In Nigeria, Amaduche, Babatunde and Adediji (2020) surveyed employees from three major commercial banks and reported that electronic banking positively influences operational performance, based on Pearson correlation results. Ibekwe (2021) further demonstrated, using OLS regression on 2006–2019 secondary data, that POS, ATM, and mobile banking transactions positively affect return on assets (ROA), indicating performance-enhancing effects of digital channels.

Beyond Nigeria, Osiolo and Sije (2023) surveyed managers from 42 Kenyan commercial banks and found that mobile banking significantly improves financial performance. However, their findings rely on subjective managerial perceptions rather than financial data, limiting insight into the actual effects of digital channels on liquidity and asset quality.

Overall, existing studies demonstrate the growing influence of digital banking channels on bank performance. Yet, empirical evidence on how internet banking specifically affects liquidity and asset quality; particularly using validated secondary financial data remains limited, especially for Nigerian commercial banks with international authorization. This gap underscores the relevance of the present study, which examines the interplay between internet banking adoption, liquidity dynamics, and asset quality using robust bank-level data.

3.0 Methods

This study employed an ex-post facto research design to examine the relationship between internet banking, liquidity, and asset quality in Nigerian commercial banks. The design was appropriate because the analysis relied on existing financial data that could not be manipulated (Kothari & Garg, 2014).

The population consisted of all eight Nigerian commercial banks with international authorization licenses listed on the Nigerian Exchange as of December 31, 2022. Given the small population, a census

sampling technique was used, and all eight banks were included. Secondary data were extracted from the audited annual reports of the banks for 2015–2022, a period that coincides with the intensification of Nigeria’s cashless policy and the expansion of internet banking services.

Data were analyzed using descriptive statistics (mean and standard deviation) and inferential techniques. Correlation analysis and panel regression were conducted, with Panel-Corrected Standard Errors (PCSE) applied based on diagnostic tests to address heteroskedasticity and contemporaneous correlation across panels.

3.1 Model Specification

The test of hypotheses in this study is based on the following models which have been specified to guide this study.

Model I

$$AQ_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 iBanking_{it} + \beta_2 COMPt_{it} + U_{it} \tag{1}$$

Model II

$$LIQ_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 iBanking_{it} + \beta_2 COMPt_{it} + U_{it} \tag{2}$$

Model III

$$AQ_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 iBanking_{it} + \beta_2 (iBanking) * (LIQ)_{it} + \beta_3 COMPt_{it} + U_{it} \tag{3}$$

The subscripts i and t a suggestion that the intercepts for the 8 banks may differ, but each of the bank’s intercept does not vary over time. The *a-priori* expectation is that $\beta_1 X_{1it} < 0$, $\beta_2 X_{2it} < 0$, $\beta_3 X_{3it} < 0$.

Table 1: Measurement and Description of Variables

Variable Type	Variable	Label	Proxy	Measurement
Dependent Variables	Asset Quality	<i>AQ</i>	Non-Performing Loan ratio.	(Total Non-Performing Loans/Total Gross Loan * 100 of bank <i>i</i> in year <i>t</i>
	Liquidity	<i>LIQ</i>	Bank Liquidity	(Liquid Assets Divided by Short term liabilities) x 100 of bank <i>i</i> in year <i>t</i>
Independent Variable	Internet Banking	<i>iBanking</i>	Log of e-banking fees and Commission	Sum of ATM charges, USSD commissions, POS, mobile and internet banking transfers of bank <i>i</i> in year <i>t</i>
Control Variables	Competitiveness	<i>COMPt</i>	Bank Competitiveness	Logarithm of total fee and commission of bank <i>i</i> in year <i>t</i>

$\beta_1 \dots \beta_3$ = Regressors
 it = Individual Banks at time t .
 ϵ = Error Term (variables not captured in the model)

4.0 Results and Discussion

This study investigated the impact of internet banking on the asset quality and liquidity of Nigerian commercial banks. The focus was on banks with international authorization licenses, given their heightened regulatory oversight by multiple authorities. The results of the analysis are presented in the following sections:

4.1 Descriptive Statistics

This section presents the descriptive statistics of the data collected for the study. The analysis includes the mean, standard deviation, minimum, and maximum values. The results are summarized in Table 2 below:

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics

Variables	Obs.	Mean	Std.Dev.	Min.	Max.
AQ	64	6.137031	5.060593	1.70	26
LIQ	64	45.72234	11.25613	30.0	75
iBanking	64	10.18594	0.394388	8.85	10.9
COMPt	64	10.64250	0.5624041	7.26	11.32

Source: Fieldwork, 2024

Table 2 presents descriptive statistics for the dataset, which comprises 64 observations; reflecting data from eight banks over eight years, thus forming a balanced panel suitable for regression analysis, as it exceeds the minimum threshold of 30 observations.

The mean values of the variables range from 6.137 (asset quality, AQ) to 45.722 (liquidity, LIQ), with standard deviations generally low, the highest being 11.256 for LIQ. This indicates limited variability relative to the overall averages. Minimum values are 1.70 for AQ, 30.0 for LIQ, 8.85 for internet banking (iBanking), and 7.26 for bank competitiveness (COMPt), while maximum values are 26 for AQ, 75 for LIQ, 10.9 for iBanking, and 11.32 for COMPt. The results confirm that the dataset is complete, with no missing observations.

4.2 Test For Normal Distribution of Data

The Shapiro-Wilk test was employed to assess the normality of the data and determine whether it follows a normal distribution. This is essential for verifying the assumptions underlying the application of the OLS regression method. The results are presented in Table 3.

Table 3: Normality Test Outcome

Variables	Obs.	W	V	Z	Prob>Z
AQ	64	0.61400	22.098	6.697	0.00000

LIQ	64	0.91003	5.151	3.546	0.00020
iBanking	64	0.96349	2.090	1.595	0.05538
COMPt	64	0.71430	16.356	6.046	0.00000

Source: Fieldwork, 2024

According to standard econometric criteria, residuals are considered normally distributed at the 5% significance level if the probability value (Prob > Z) exceeds 0.05. Values below this threshold indicate deviations from normality. In this study, the residuals for internet banking (iBanking) yielded a Prob > Z of 0.05538, slightly above 0.05, suggesting that they are approximately normally distributed. Conversely, the residuals for asset quality (AQ), liquidity (LIQ), and bank competitiveness (COMPt) produced Prob > Z values below 0.05, indicating non-normality. This implies that the normality assumption required for OLS regression is not fully satisfied. Consequently, a regression approach that adjusts for standard errors is necessary. Nevertheless, it remains appropriate to examine correlations among the variables prior to conducting further diagnostic tests. The results of this analysis are presented in the following section.

4.3 Correlation Analysis

Since the residuals for some of the data did not follow a normal distribution curve, the Spearman Rank Correlation Coefficient (Spearman rho) was used to examine the relationship between internet banking, liquidity and the asset quality of banks in Nigeria. The Spearman rho result is shown in Table 4.

Table 4: Correlation Analysis

	AQ	LIQ	iBanking	COMPt
AQ	1.0000			
LIQ	-0.0214 (0.8666)	1.0000		
iBanking	-0.0107 (0.9332)	0.3503* (0.0045)	1.0000	
COMPt	-0.0324 (0.7994)	0.5350* (0.0000)	0.8796* (0.0000)	1.0000

Source: Fieldwork, 2024

*significant at 5%

With the result of the correlation analysis presented in Table 4, the existence of a linear relationship could be established between internet banking and measures of the regressands (LIQ and AQ). Note that LIQ, iBanking and COMPt exhibited weak and negative correlation with AQ; whereas, iBanking and COMPt, exhibited a strong and positive correlation with LIQ. Also, it can be observed that the correlation between iBanking and COMPt is positive and very strong. Notwithstanding, the correlation

coefficient of 0.8796 for iBanking and COMPt is very high, indicating the possible presence of multicollinearity; hence the dataset for these variables were further subjected to the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) test to ascertain whether multicollinearity is present or not.

4.4 Tests for Multicollinearity and Heteroscedasticity

Table 5: Result for Multicollinearity Test

Variables	VIF	1/VIF
COMPt	1.57	0.637393
iBanking	1.57	0.637393
Mean VIF	1.57	

Source: Fieldwork, 2024

The VIF values from Table 5 are 1.57 for both COMPt and iBanking, with a mean VIF of 1.57. These values are well below the threshold of 10 (Jeroh, 2016; Jeroh, 2016a; Ukolobi & Jeroh, 2020; Jeroh, 2020; Izukwe & Jeroh, 2022; Ogieh & Jeroh, 2023; Jeroh, 2023; Ukavwe & Jeroh, 2024). This indicates that, despite a strong correlation between COMPt and iBanking, multicollinearity is not a concern, and including both variables in the same model is unlikely to produce unreliable estimates.

Table 6: Heteroscedasticity Test

Breusch-Pagan /Cook-Weisberg Test	
Chi2(1)	0.29
Prob > chi2	0.5927

Source: Fieldwork, 2024

The heteroscedasticity test yielded a $\chi^2(1)$ value of 0.29 with a corresponding probability of 0.5927, indicating constant variance in the residuals and the absence of heteroscedasticity. Although the data show no issues with multicollinearity or heteroscedasticity, the non-normality of residuals prevents the use of OLS regression for hypothesis testing. To address this, a more robust technique capable of accommodating non-normal residuals was employed. Accordingly, the hypotheses were tested using panel regression with Panel-Corrected Standard Errors (PCSE), which adjusts for contemporaneous correlation and provides reliable estimates under these conditions.

4.5. Test of Hypotheses and Discussion of Findings

4.5.1 Hypothesis One

Table 7: Result for Test of Hypothesis One

AQ	Coeff.	Std. Err.	Z	P > z	Decision
iBanking	0.4356482	1.507953	0.29	0.773	Do Not Reject Null Hypothesis
COMPt	-0.1872901	0.5826895	-0.32	0.748	
_CONS	3.692782	12.6349	0.29	0.770	
Obs.			64		
Wald chi2(3)			0.12		

Prob > chi2	0.9427
R-Squared	0.0007

Source: Fieldwork, 2024 *significant at 5%

In testing Hypothesis One, internet banking (iBanking) exhibited a positive coefficient of 0.436, while bank competitiveness (COMPt) showed a negative coefficient of -0.187, indicating that iBanking is positively associated with asset quality (AQ), whereas COMPt has a negative association. The standard errors were low (1.508 for iBanking and 0.583 for COMPt), suggesting that the model provides precise and reliable estimates.

However, the z-statistics indicate that neither iBanking ($z = 0.29, p = 0.773$) nor COMPt ($z = -0.32, p = 0.748$) independently exert a significant effect on asset quality. The Wald $\chi^2(2)$ statistic of 0.12 ($p = 0.9427$) further confirms that, at the 5% significance level, internet banking does not have a significant impact on the asset quality of Nigerian commercial banks. Consequently, the null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between internet banking and asset quality cannot be rejected. This finding implies that, in this context, internet banking adoption is not a significant determinant of asset quality, contrasting with evidence from Pakistan, where Rauf, Qiang, and Sajid (2014) reported a significant positive effect.

4.5.2 Hypothesis Two

Table 8: Result for Test of Hypothesis Two

LIQ	Coeff.	Std. Err.	Z	P > z	Decision
iBanking	4.89165	2.661916	1.84	0.066	Reject Null Hypothesis
COMPt	6.743341	2.395168	2.82*	0.005	
_CONS	-75.8697	19.5354	-3.88*	0.000	
Obs.			64		
Wald chi2(3)			40.57		
Prob > chi2			0.0000		
R-Squared			0.2124		

Source: Fieldwork, 2024 *significant at 5%

In testing Hypothesis Two, internet banking (iBanking) and bank competitiveness (COMPt) exhibited positive coefficients of 4.892 and 6.743, respectively. This indicates that a one-unit increase in internet banking activities corresponds to a 4.892-unit increase in bank liquidity, while a one-unit increase in competitiveness results in a 6.743-unit increase in liquidity. The standard errors were relatively low, with iBanking recording 2.662, suggesting that the model provides precise and reliable estimates.

The z-statistics reveal that iBanking alone does not significantly influence liquidity ($z = 1.84, p = 0.066$), whereas COMPt exerts a significant positive effect ($z = 2.82, p = 0.005$). However, the Wald $\chi^2(2)$ statistic of 40.57 ($p < 0.001$) indicates that, jointly, internet banking and competitiveness significantly

affect liquidity at the 5% significance level. Consequently, the null hypothesis that internet banking has no significant impact on liquidity is rejected. These findings suggest that internet banking, alongside increasing competitiveness, is a significant determinant of liquidity in Nigerian commercial banks, corroborating prior studies that report a positive influence of digital banking on bank performance (Rauf, Qiang & Sajid, 2014; Yasin, 2018).

4.5.2 Hypothesis Three

Table 9: Result for Test of Hypothesis Three

AQ	Coeff.	Std. Err.	z	P > z	Decision
iBanking	0.340631	2.067303	0.16	0.869	Do Not Reject Null Hypothesis
iBanking*LIQ	0.000986	.0080895	0.12	0.903	
COMPt	-0.255063	.6696992	-0.38	0.703	
_CONS	4.921058	20.14164	0.24	0.807	
Obs.			64		
Wald chi2(3)			0.24		
Prob > chi2			0.9700		
R-Squared			0.0011		

Source: Fieldwork, 2024

*significant at 5%

In testing Hypothesis Three, internet banking (iBanking) exhibited a positive coefficient of 0.341, while bank competitiveness (COMPt) showed a negative coefficient of -0.255, indicating that, even with liquidity included as a moderating variable, iBanking maintains a positive association with asset quality (AQ), whereas COMPt remains negatively associated. The standard errors were low (2.067 for iBanking and 0.670 for COMPt), suggesting that the model provides precise and reliable estimates.

The z-statistics show that neither iBanking ($z = 0.16, p = 0.869$) nor COMPt ($z = -0.38, p = 0.703$) independently exert a significant effect on asset quality. Furthermore, the Wald $\chi^2(2)$ statistic of 0.24 ($p = 0.970$) indicates that, at the 5% significance level, liquidity does not significantly moderate the relationship between internet banking and asset quality. Consequently, the null hypothesis that liquidity does not significantly moderate the effect of internet banking on asset quality cannot be rejected. This finding implies that variations in bank liquidity arising from internet banking adoption do not significantly influence the relationship between digital banking and asset quality in Nigerian commercial banks, a result that contrasts with prior studies (Rauf, Qiang & Sajid, 2014).

5.0 Conclusion and Recommendations

The adoption of internet banking and its interaction with liquidity and asset quality has become increasingly relevant due to the growing role of technology in banking and the widespread use of online platforms by customers. The integration of ICT has transformed the timing, nature, and scale of banking services, compelling banks to continuously adapt strategies to meet evolving customer demands. In

today's competitive banking environment, commercial banks must efficiently leverage their resources to enhance performance and liquidity while maintaining sound asset quality.

While previous studies have largely focused on the relationship between online banking and overall bank performance, this study highlights the specific interplay between internet banking, liquidity, and asset quality in commercial banks with international authorization licenses. The findings indicate that, in Nigeria, internet banking has a significant positive impact on bank liquidity but does not significantly influence asset quality. These insights underscore the need for banks to balance digital innovation with robust risk management practices to sustain financial stability and competitiveness.

Based on these outcomes of this study, it was recommended that:

- iii. Commercial banks maintain strict compliance with credit management guidelines to safeguard asset quality in the face of expanding internet banking services.
- iv. Efforts should be made by commercial banks to develop strategies that would continuously increase the level of customers patronage of internet banking services and platforms.
- v. The management of banks should make practical efforts aimed at developing useful internet banking products and should consider embarking on the sensitization of bank customers on the benefits derivable from such internet banking products and services.

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